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MS8- Magnet Layout decision and engineering design report of the curved CCT dipole magnet demonstrator for the HITRIPlus project

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DOCUMENT SUMMARY

The Heavy Ion Therapy Research Integration plus (HITRIplus) European H2020 project aims at bringing together, integrating on European scale, and opening up to European researchers from academia and industry, the key research infrastructures for bio-physics and medical research on cancer treatment with heavy ion beams, jointly developing at the same time the next generation of its sophisticated instruments. One of the major goals is to work out a reference design for a superconducting synchrotron with a footprint of about 8×8 m, and develop the prototypes of its key components. This report is the summary of the results of Task 8.3, "Preliminary Engineering Design for Accelerator and Gantry magnets", presenting the functional specifications of the bending magnets, the developments, considerations and tests carried out, and the mechanical design of the prototype.

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1 Introduction

Charged hadron beams (protons or heavier ions) offer a great advantage in the treatment of cancer. Due to their different energy deposition profile compared to X-rays, a much sharper contrast can be realized between the damage to the healthy tissues and the tumour. While proton therapy centers are nowadays widespread, most of them use commercial turn-key cyclotrons, which offer limited flexibility. These can also not be scaled for heavier ions, which have a higher magnetic rigidity than protons with the same penetration depth in human tissue, and therefore require either larger accelerators or higher magnetic fields. The 4 European carbon-ion centers use normal-conducting synchrotrons with a diameter of around 25 m which is a clear block in the way of spreading this treatment method. Only one of them, the Heidelberg Ion Therapy Center possesses a gantry, weighing a total of 600 tons.

The HITRIPlus European H2020 project [1] was launched in April 2021 as a common effort between academia and industry with the aim, among others, to develop the reference design of a compact superconducting synchrotron with a footprint of 8×8 m and build prototypes of its key components. Work package 8 ("Superconducting magnet design") has the objective to perform a first technical and financial assessment of different magnet designs for a novel type of carbon ion synchrotron and gantry complex (completed [2, 3]) and to design and build a prototype magnet demonstrating the feasibility of the necessary features for both the ring and gantry magnets.

This task is very challenging. There are no successful precedents; so far only one curved superconducting CCT magnet has been fabricated and tested [4] which failed by a high-voltage breakdown, presumably due to the construction concept of its formers (winding mandrel). The relatively high field (4 Tesla) calls for a careful mechanical design. The curved nature of the magnet makes the manufacturing of the formers very difficult. The high ramp rate (1 T/s for the ring magnets, 0.4 T/s for the demonstrator prototype) restricts the conductivity of the formers' material to low values. The goal to achieve conductive cooling requires materials with good heat conductivity, which is conflicting with the previous requirement. The first, common demonstrator prototype for both the gantry and ring magnets, to be constructed within the framework of this project, would leave a lot of further R&D efforts necessary until the final magnets can be built and installed in a medical facility. Aggressive weight optimization for the gantry magnets and the implementation of conductive cooling (dropped from the original list of goals for the demonstrator) are just two examples.

This document is the milestone MS8 of the work package, the preliminary engineering design of the demonstrator prototype. Under the circumstances described above, the working group has decided to extend the scope of the document beyond the simple presentation of a design. It summarizes the requirements, guidelines, efforts, ideas, tests, alternative concepts, and analyses as well in order to serve as a basis for the later stage of the R&D activities, emphasizing possibilities having potential but not yet fully exploited by the time of writing this document. Simulations and analyses published elsewhere are not reproduced in this document but only cited. Simulations not yet published elsewhere are included if they have an important impact on the mechanical design.

The document is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes the parameters of the demonstrator prototype including a quick reasoning and design guidelines that have led to the choice of a particular parameter value, design concept, or material. Section 3 defines the magnet topology. Sections 4-6 discuss mechanical issues (manufacturing of the formers, mechanical and thermal expansion issues, winding). Section 7 describes the mathematical parameterization of the winding geometry and briefly describes the magnetic analysis method to derive the parameters (shape) of the winding, together with the values of the optimized parameters. This section also includes a relatively long magnetic analysis of the effect of parallel-faced yoke laminations with interleaving tapered air gaps instead of tapered laminations with a 100% fill factor, since this concept could allow a notably different mechanical design of the yoke, and cost savings. The mechanical design is presen-

ted in the last section (8). The baseline design is developed by CERN/INFN using tapered laminations. This concept is well developed and is supported by extensive FEM simulations [5] An alternative concept is presented as well which uses parallel-faced laminations and offers some advantages but is lacking the same level of simulations at the time of writing this document.

2 Functional specifications, parameters and design guidelines

The original HITRIplus synchrotron design of the project proposal was based on a rectangular layout with a footprint of about 8×8 m [6]. Bending magnets at the corners must provide 90° total deflection to the beam and have Alternating-Gradient (AG) layers nested inside [7]. For the sake of simpler design and construction, they can be realized by three magnets each bending the beam by $22.5^\circ - 45^\circ - 22.5^\circ$, however the resulting layout will loose in compactness because of the extension of the magnets ends. The baseline today [8] is a triangular layout with 120° bending at the corners, realized by 2 dipole magnets, with nested AG layers, of 60° and a strong (superconducting) quadrupole in between.

Building upon a preliminary gantry design [9], an extensive exploratory study [10, 11] has brought to the selection of an optimal gantry configuration based on four equal 4 T 45° dipoles. The gantry optics layout was optimized to have pure dipoles with concentrated quadrupolar gradients in the proximity of the magnets' heads. These gradients could be obtained with specific CCT nested windings or with dedicated spool-piece quadrupoles [12]. The current layout measures 14 meters in length and 5.75 meters in height, leaving about 3 meters between the scanning magnets, downstream of the last dipole, and the isocenter.

Cost of manufacturing and spare parts management favour non-diverse hardware. This principle was followed in the current project by considering whether it is worth or possible to use the same bending magnets in both the ring and the gantry. However, since the requirements for the ring and gantry magnets are different (aggressive weight optimization and size reduction for the gantry and higher ramp rate for the synchrotron), and the design of such a novel magnet prototype is quite challenging anyway, the consortium has decided to design and build a demonstrator which does not have the same parameters and/or characteristics as any of these two types of magnets, but demonstrates the feasibility of the key features for both.

The bending radius of the gantry magnets must be less than 2 m, and as small as possible, in order to keep the total dimension of the gantry reasonably low. The magnetic field of the bending magnets is determined by the highest magnetic rigidity of the accelerated ion species: carbon C^{12} ions with an energy of 430 MeV/u, sufficient to reach a penetration depth of 33 cm in human tissue. The corresponding magnetic rigidity is $B\rho=6.6$ T m. The bending radius and magnetic field of the magnet were chosen to be $\rho=1650$ mm and $B_0=4$ T, respectively. This fulfills the requirement of the bending radius being less than 2 m and is considered realizable from the magnetic point of view.

In order to shorten the synchrotron cycle as much as possible, the highest achievable ramp rates should be realized. A ramp rate of 1 T/s was set as a goal for the ring magnets (with the possibility to compromise on the maximum bending field and curvature radius), resulting in an acceleration period of 10 s. For the demonstrator, the lower value 0.4 T/s of the gantry magnet was chosen.

For the sake of compactness of the ring layout, the installed magnets are planned to be nested bending+focusing magnets. The focusing functionality would most probably be added as an extra pair of winding layers of the CCT magnet, in order to provide independent tunability of the optics. However, the high ramp rate (calling for non-conductive formers), the curved geometry of the magnet, and the 4 T field are considered challenging enough for the first-of-its-kind demonstrator prototype. Therefore a pure dipole magnet with only two CCT layers was chosen as the magnet configuration. A focusing field can be superimposed in later prototypes by

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an additional pair of winding layers.

The magnet aperture of 80 mm is defined by the beam optics requirements.

In order to simplify the infrastructure and installation, and facilitate daily operation, the gantry magnets should use cryo-coolers, without the need for external liquid helium supply. After the careful assessment of the challenges of designing and constructing a curved, 4 T magnet, this goal was given up for the first demonstrator prototype, which would therefore be tested in a bath-type cryostat. One of the first priorities for further R&D shall be the development of a dry magnet.

The choice of the superconducting wire was driven by the fact that one of the beneficiaries of the project (INFN-Milano) has a significant repository of low-loss NbTi strands left over from the DISCORAP project [13]. This strand has a Cu/SC ratio of 1.36, and a bare diameter of 0.821mm. This strand has about 20% lower critical current than the similar LHC strands (LHC02 or outer layer strand) [14]. The high-luminosity LHC corrector CCT magnets [15, 16] used only 2×5 strands of the LHC type wound into 2×5 mm grooves machined into aluminium formers. The higher field of the current demonstrator (4 T instead of 3 T), the 20% lower critical current, and the larger rib (wall between neighbouring grooves in the formers) thickness (around 0.8 mm for insulators such as PEEK or pre-preg, instead of the 0.4 mm achieved in metals), i.e. a less dense winding require a larger number of conductors, which presumably can not be maintained in an organized grid pattern within the groove during winding. The uninsulated strands are therefore organized in 6-around-1 twisted ropes: 6 superconducting strands twisted around a central Cu strand. The Cu strand serves the purpose of better windability. This strand configuration has a factor of 6/9 lower density of superconducting strands with respect to a rectangular pattern (3×3 strands). These factors lead finally to a significantly larger number of superconducting strands compared to [15, 16]. In order to allow the fast ramp rate (calling for lower magnet inductance), and decrease the number of splices, all conductors of a rope are connected in parallel, and splices will be made on a rope-to-rope (and not strand-to-strand) level. Replacing the central Cu strand with a superconducting strand, keeping the total rope current unchanged would reduce the current carried by the individual superconducting strands. This possibility is kept as a later fallback solution to increase the operating margin without changing the magnet geometry if required. The ropes will have a double layer of braided polyester insulation.

An iron yoke is installed around the winding in order to boost the magnetic field in the aperture, decouple the aperture from the environment of the magnet (i.e. reduce the stray field of the magnet in its surrounding, and shield the aperture from external magnetic disturbances), and to give mechanical support to the coil, compensating the Lorentz forces acting on the windings. The thickness of the yoke was defined to be 100 mm, in agreement with [17]. Since weight optimization is a very important goal for gantry magnets, those magnets may need a yoke-less design developed at a later stage.

The values of the parameters for the ring, gantry and demonstrator magnets are summarized in Table 1.

3 Magnet layout and topology

The report [3] described and compared different superconducting magnet concepts for the HITRIPlus project. The conclusion of that work was that a NbTi-based CCT magnet has favourable characteristics with respect to other choices. Since this magnet topology is less explored today than the cos-theta design and is experiencing a vivid R&D activity by many research labs, one can expect a significant evolution of this concept. Therefore this design was chosen for the demonstrator prototype, contributing to the global efforts, and hopefully benefiting from future advancements.

CCT magnets have two layers of canted solenoid-like windings. While some early prototypes wound the

Table 1: Parameters of the prototype. Parameters typeset in boldface are determined by external constraints, not subject to optimization. TBD stands for “to be defined”. Further parameters of the magnet are listed in Table 7.

Parameter	Symbol	Value			Unit
		Ring	Gantry	Demonstrator	
Maximum beam rigidity	$B\rho$	6.6			T m
Nominal field	B_0	4	4	4	T
Nominal gradient		t.b.d.	t.b.d.	0	T/m
Ramp rate	dB/dt	1	0.4	0.4	T/s
Bore diameter	D_{ap}	80	80	80	mm
Spar thickness	t_{spar}	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	8	mm
Bending radius	ρ	1650	1650	1650	mm
Bending angle		30, 40 or 60	30, 45 or 90	30	degree
Strand diameter		t.b.d.	t.b.d.	0.821	mm
Filament diameter		t.b.d.	t.b.d.	3.5	μm
Conductor		6+1 or 7+0 rope		6+1 rope	
Rope diameter	D_w	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	2.53	mm
Cu/SC ratio	λ	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	1.36	
Number of conductors	$n_1 \times n_2$	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	2×8	
Groove size	$d_1 \times d_2$	t.b.d.	t.b.d.	5.7×22.8	mm
Inductance	L			103	mH
Splices		Outside of magnet, strand-by-strand			
Operating temperature	T_{op}	4.5	4.5	4.5	K
Min. margin on load line		t.b.d.	t.b.d.	20	%
Cooling		Cryocooler	Cryocooler	He bath	
Yoke		yes	?	yes	

two layers separately and joined the two windings by splicing at both ends of the magnet, the HL-LHC twin-aperture orbit correctors introduced a so-called "layer-jump" between the two layers, i.e. the conductors transitioning from the inner layer to the outer layer without interruption at one end of the magnet [18]. Since this greatly reduces the number of joints (possible sources of mistakes and losses), and there are working design concepts for this problem, this project has adapted this choice. Splices at the other end of the magnet will be implemented on a rope-to-rope level (i.e. two twisted ropes being joined together rather than their strands individually). The "praying hands" configuration (where the ends of the jointed wires are oriented in the same direction) shows a current distribution pattern changing with the magnet current, and has a dynamic behavior for ramped magnets [19] like the current prototype. This configuration has a resistance depending on the current [20]. The "shaking hands" configuration (the ends of the two wires oriented in opposite directions) has a current-independent resistance [20]. Therefore the latter was selected for the prototype. The splices will be installed outside of the magnet to provide access and the possibility for repair in case of an eventual splice failure.

4 Choice of former materials, challenges

Due to the high ramp rate the choice of materials for the magnet, and especially for the formers is of crucial importance. The conductivity of the formers must be as low as possible, otherwise eddy currents would distort the field, introduce a time lag of the field with respect to the ramped magnet current, and heat the coils.

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Another important point is the machinability of the chosen material, and the minimum rib thickness between neighbouring grooves, since this has a significant impact on the transfer function of the magnet, i.e. the current (or the number of conductors) required to reach a given field.

Aluminium was excluded due to its unacceptably high conductivity [17], and the following materials were considered acceptable.

4.1 Stainless steel, 3D printed

Stainless steel has high strength and is a widespread material in many applications. 3D printing was considered a possible technology. This process typically creates a hollow mesh structure (STL - Standard Triangle Language) cad model, which - when optimized correctly - delivers high strength, but drastically reduces the amount of material, thereby the weight and cost, thanks to the geometric freedom of design. In addition, such a structure would possess a reduced electric conductivity with respect to a bulk piece.

The company Egile Ltd (Spain) first produced two small test samples featuring a small fraction of the former geometry (Fig. 1a,b). Then, 90 mm high sections of both the inner and outer formers were printed in the same process in a nested configuration in order to increase productivity (Fig. 1c), with a gap of 1 mm separating them. The layer thickness of the printing process was 60 μm . Although this two-in-one printing procedure is time and cost-efficient, the evacuation of the powder from the deep grooves of the inner former was difficult, leading to problems during the stress relief heat treatment: the powder became solid and made the removal of the support very difficult in the later stage. The fine mesh-like support structure visible in Fig. 1c was necessary everywhere where the ribs had an angle to the horizontal plane below 45°. The maximum distortion measured on the inner and outer contours of the two formers, before stress relief heat treatments and their removal from the printing platform, was 0.29 mm.

The test pieces were then heat-treated for stress relief and to provide them adequate mechanical properties, following the standard AMS 2759/4, and separated from the printing platform. The support mesh was removed by hand using a vibrating pneumatic chisel. The surfaces uncovered this way were polished using a rotary grinding wheel. After this, scotch polishing and fine-grained white corundum sandblasting has been applied (Fig. 1d). The largest measured deviations from the CAD model were around 0.38 mm (Fig. 2). Extrapolation of these results to the maximally possible 200 mm height is around 0.55 mm.

With today's printers, the size of the pieces is limited to a few-10 cm typically. This makes it necessary to manufacture the formers from several segments. Assembly of these segments into a rigid structure is challenging, especially due to the dense system of laminations. As for any technologies where the segments are first manufactured with all the grooves, and then attached to build up the entire length of the former, there is a high risk of producing sharp steps on the internal wall of the grooves, which can lead to the damage and failure of the winding insulation. This was the most probable cause of the failure of the first curved CCT prototype developed at LBNL [4]. Given these difficulties, this choice was not considered further for the demonstrator.

As an alternative, Ti6Al4V is another material widely used in additive manufacturing with low conductivity. However, its tendency for deformations is higher than that of stainless steel, and was therefore not tested.

4.2 Pre-preg

The manufacturing of hollow, curved tubes with a thick wall from a pre-preg material (glass fiber cloth pre-impregnated by resin), wound and hardened on a collapsible mandrel was reported to be a mature technology,

Figure 1: 3D printed stainless steel test pieces by Egile Ltd, Spain. Initial test pieces (a,b), the 2 formers on the printing platform (c) and the outer former after the removing of the support structure from the grooves(d).

* Arrow show directions of deviations with respect to CAD (shrinkage)

Figure 2: Dimensional control results of the outer test piece after heat treatment, removal from the platform and support removal.

ready for application, by a company working in this field. A series of tests was conducted on a flat block of pre-preg material to study the minimum feasible rib thickness between two neighbouring grooves (Fig. 3). A relatively thin glass fiber pre-preg was used for this test, a 300 gram $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fiber with an epoxy resin system. This resulted in an approximated layer thickness of 0.3 mm per layer and a consistent build-up through the layers which is beneficial during the milling stage. The quality of the hardened material was checked under the microscope. The material showed a good quality without voids. Sinusoidal grooves were machined into the material with a dimension of 5.7(width) \times 27(depth) mm. The rib thickness between neighbouring grooves was varying from 2.2 down to 1.4 mm in 0.1 mm steps. The lower value was proposed by the company, driven by the fear that a thinner wall would break already during manufacturing, due to the intrinsically laminated structure of the material. Even the thinnest wall showed good stability, and 10 more grooves were planned to be machined into the same workpiece with wall thicknesses down to 0.4 mm in 0.1 mm steps. Unfortunately, communication from the company ceased for unknown reasons. Due to the deadlines of the project, and parallel advances in tests with other materials, this material was dropped from the list of candidates for the demonstrator prototype. However, it is still considered a feasible and cost-effective alternative and should be considered in later R&D projects.

Even though the goal to demonstrate conductive cooling was given up for the first demonstrator prototype, this has to be addressed in a later development stage. As an insulator, pre-preg has the great advantage of completely suppressing eddy currents, but has the drawback of lower heat conductivity, which would be of primary importance for conductive cooling. Copper wires embedded in the composite could improve heat conductivity without introducing eddy currents if they do not form closed loops. This idea could be exploited in a later development stage.

4.3 PEEK GF30

PEEK (polyether ether ketone) is an outstanding high-performance thermoplastic material, often advertised as “metal replacement”. Being an insulator, it eliminates eddy current losses and heating in the formers. While pure PEEK (similarly to other plastics) has a much higher thermal expansion than metals, the variant with 30% glass fiber content matches stainless steel and aluminium-bronze in this property. Glass fibers also serve as reinforcement, strengthening the material. The glass fibers may be present either in the form of short, randomly oriented chips, resulting in an isotropic material (for example in the case of compression-molded semi-finished products produced from pellets or powder which already contain the fiber chips, or by the mixture and co-extrusion of glass fiber chips and pellets, as done in [21]), or in the form of woven layers with long fibers, resulting in an anisotropic structure with higher strength along the layers (glass fiber layers and PEEK powder stacked in a hot compression dye). PEEK also has high radiation tolerance [22], an important property for accelerator components, and keeps its excellent mechanical properties at cryogenic temperatures as well [22].

Although PEEK with carbon fiber or glass fiber fillers can be 3D printed, and several commercial vendors offer this service, the reliability and tolerances of this manufacturing method were questioned by several experts. Due to its high melting temperature, the 3D printing process requires dedicated printing heads and a delicate temperature control of the entire printer chamber. Tensile tests on 3D printed glass fiber loaded PEEK samples [23] indicated a very anisotropic behaviour, with low flexural strength in the direction normal to the printed layers (minimum measured value for 5 samples is 23 MPa) and high flexural strength in the other two directions (150-190 MPa). Due to the size limitation of PEEK 3D printers (<600 mm in general) the formers would be constructed from several segments containing the grooves. The rigid attachment of these segments would be difficult. Given these inputs, and lacking more time and resources, 3D printed PEEK GF30 was dropped from the list of candidate materials.

Figure 3: Test piece manufactured from a pre-preg material to test the minimum feasible rib thickness.

A series of tests was conducted on pure PEEK and PEEK with 30% glass fiber content to establish the minimum feasible wall thickness (Fig. 4), with groove depths 5, 10, 15 and 25 mm. Pure PEEK behaved better in this test, ribs with the smallest tested thickness of 0.5 mm were stable. Ribs with the same thickness in PEEK with 30% glass fiber content broke during machining for groove depths of 20 and 25 mm. Ribs with a thickness of 0.8 mm survived the machining for all groove depths. In the real case scenario, several factors make the rib mechanically more stable. The ribs are on a cylindrical, curving surface, with minimum thickness at their bottom corner, and a significantly ($\sim 50\%$) larger thickness at the top of the groove for these parameters. The thickness is also gradually increasing along the groove, away from the minimum position. The minimum value of 0.8 mm was therefore accepted as the minimum value for this material.

For PEEK, the limited range of stock material shapes and sizes is a drawback. It makes necessary to construct the formers by gluing together several parts, which is an extra complication, and to remove a significant amount of the raw material during CNC machining. This, combined with the relatively high price of the material (180-200 euro/kg) makes this choice presumably expensive. Compression moulding of pre-parts with only a little geometric margin, and retouching on a CNC machine to have the final accuracy was considered as a viable alternative to drastically reduce the material loss and to benefit from the reduced price of the material sold in the form of pellets. Due to the limited time and resources, this option was finally not considered for

Figure 4: Rib thickness tests on pure and GF30 PEEK

the demonstrator but should be kept on the list for further R&D work beyond the time span of this project.

In order to test the reliability of glued joints between PEEK surfaces, three sets of tensile test samples were prepared.

- Bulk PEEK GF30 sample without glued interface as reference, with 6 mm diameter, and M10 threads for mounting.
- Normal-direction glued sample (see Fig. 5)
- Shear-direction glued sample

The raw material was a 10 mm diameter rod with 30% glass fiber content, purchased from Boedeker Plastics [24]. 12-12 test samples for both the normal-direction and shear-direction tests, respectively, were glued in a jig and clamped down into V-shaped grooves ensuring coaxiality between the two parts. For the normal-direction samples, a light axial force was applied from one end using bolts (see Fig. 6). Stycast 2850 FT epoxy was used with two different catalysers: 23LV and 24LV. 6 samples were prepared with both catalysers, 3 to be tested at room temperature, and 6 in liquid nitrogen.

Figure 5: Tensile test piece for PEEK+Stycast, normal direction.

Figure 6: Setup for the gluing of the PEEK-Stycast tensile test samples (normal-direction tensile tests).

Table 2: Mechanical properties of PEEK GF30.

	Measured	Boedeker (this mat.) [24]	Ketron PEEK GF30 [28]	TECAPEEK GF30 [29]	Solvay Ket-aSpire [30]
Tensile modulus [GPa]	5-6	6.2	7	6.3	10.5
Tensile strength [MPa]	80	103	80	113	160

The tests were carried out by the University of Miskolc, Hungary. The pure PEEK GF30 samples had a tensile modulus of 5-6 GPa, tensile stress at yield (offset 0.2%) of 54-57 MPa, and maximum tensile stress of 79-81 at room temperature (3 samples). The experimental values are compared to the specification of the vendor of this material, and two other vendors, in Table 2. The stress vs. strain curves are shown in Fig. 7. The glued samples had a surprisingly bad performance and broke very easily. The maximum tensile stress was 2, 17, 18 MPa and 24, 24, 26 MPa in the normal direction for the catalysers 24LV and 23LV, respectively. For the shear-direction samples the maximum tensile stress values were 2, 5, 5 MPa and 3, 5, 5 MPa for the catalysers 24LV and 23LV, respectively. Figures 8 and 9 show the glued surfaces after breakage. Since the flexural strength of Stycast with catalyst 23LV is 106 MPa [25] (according to [26] the tensile strength is 60 MPa, which could not be verified from official data sheets), this result demonstrates a weak adhesion to PEEK. Discouraged by these results, the similar samples have not been tested in liquid nitrogen. Further tests with Stycast 2850 FT + Catalyst 23LV with different surface preparation (roughening, etc), and other epoxies (for example the MasterBond EP29LPSP [27]), as well as consultations with the epoxy vendors are in progress.

Figure 7: Tensile stress vs. strain curve of 3 bulk PEEK GF30 samples at room temperature.

Figure 8: Photos of the tensile test samples of PEEK GF30 with Stycast 2850 FT + Catalyst 23LV

Figure 9: Photos of the tensile test samples of PEEK GF30 with Stycast 2850 FT + Catalyst 24LV

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Further ideas in the plastic line, which could be potentially exploited in a later stage, are as follows:

- Use other high-performance plastics.

PEI (polyetherimide, Ultem) with 30% glass fiber has similar radiation tolerance as PEEK [22, 31], and similar or better mechanical properties (tensile modulus of 9.5 GPa [32] or 5.3 GPa [33], tensile strength of 165 MPa [32] or 135 MPa [33]) but is somewhat cheaper, and is easier to process. As an example, the thickest (95 mm) sheet of PEEK with 30% glass fiber content available from Ensinger Plastics would contain significant remanent stresses, while an Ultem sheet with the same thickness would have no problems, and would cost about 15% less, according to information obtained in consultations with the company.

PAI (polyamide-imide, Torlon 5030) has excellent radiation tolerance [22, 31], and mechanical properties similar to or outperforming PEEK (tensile modulus of 6.9 GPa [34] or 14.5 GPa [35], and tensile strength of 159 MPa [34] or 205 MPa [35]).

- Cu wires embedded in the compression-moulded composite to increase heat conductivity (see discussion at the end of section 4.2)

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4.4 Aluminium-bronze

Aluminium-bronze has low electrical conductivity, is easily available as raw material, and has good manufacturing properties. As for all non-additive manufacturing processes, the machining of the precise inner surface of the long (~ 1 m) curved tube is challenging. For aluminium-bronze the following manufacturing methods were considered.

- Bending a straight tube. Due to the better availability of aluminium tubes, a test with an AW-6060 tube was made by the company AGCM-Alpes with nominal diameters ID/OD=100/130 mm. The measured inner diameter of the tube was 129.8 ± 0.1 mm. The tube was bent without heating to a bending radius of $\rho=2000$ mm. After bending, the measured inner diameters at the two ends were between 127.4-131.5 mm and 127.8-130.65 mm. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 10. Bending the tube with this wall thickness was already challenging, application of the same process to a thicker tube (~ 30 mm wall thickness) is not straightforward. Due to these distortions the tube, as-bent, can not be used directly for the formers.
- Two half tubes (split along the horizontal midplane of the magnet) are manufactured first, either from a bulk material, or by cutting a bent tube in two halves. The inner and midplane surfaces are precisely machined on a CNC machine. For the case of a bent tube, this step removes the distorted surfaces resulting from the bending process. The two halves are then joined either by vacuum brazing or electron beam welding. The grooves are machined onto the outer surface as the last step, ensuring that no sharp steps are produced at the interface of the components.
- Another manufacturing alternative is that being tested in the project *Fusillo*. Longitudinal segments of the formers are attached using a dove-tail interface. Before assembly, the male part is cooled in liquid nitrogen, whereas the female part is warmed by hot air. This allows the male interface to be inserted into the female interface. The two close tightly after reaching the same temperature. This is a similar technique used by LBNL [4], with the exception that the grooves are machined into the formers after the assembly, avoiding potential sharp steps on the inner walls of the ribs at the interfaces, which have led to the high voltage breakdown of the LBNL magnet.

In order to gain experience with the manufacturing of the material and establish the minimum possible wall thickness, a straight former was manufactured in the CERN workshop (Fig. 11). The grooves were machined with a rounded tool to eliminate the sharp corners at the bottom of the groove. This slightly reduces the minimum rib thickness, eliminates a stress accumulation point, and reduces the empty volume to be filled by the impregnant. The minimum rib thicknesses varied from 1.24 to 0.74 mm in 0.1 mm steps. All ribs were mechanically very stable. For this material, a minimum rib thickness of 0.4 mm is accepted, based on the experience from other projects.

Figure 10: Measurement results of the bending tests on an AW-6060 tube.

Figure 11: Straight aluminium-bronze test former machined in the CERN main workshop, with varying rib thicknesses.

Table 3: Comparison of the materials considered for manufacturing the formers

	Stainless steel	Aluminium-bronze	PEEK (or PAI, PEI) GF30	Pre-preg
Technology	3D printing	CNC machining of half curved tubes (inside surface) either from bulk plate, or from a bent tube cut in 1/2, brazing or e-beam welding, CNC machining of grooves	Gluing of thick plates, CNC machining of half tubes, gluing, CNC machining of grooves	Winding & hardening on a collapsible mandrel, CNC machining of grooves
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Strength – 3D printing produces mesh-like structure, reducing conductivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Good machinability – Good heat conductivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – No eddy currents – Good machinability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – No eddy currents – Technology readiness level 9/10 – Entire former directly manufactured as a single piece – Very efficient usage of raw material
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Deformation, tolerances – Difficulty assembling a rigid former from segments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Eddy currents – AC losses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Limited availability of raw materials – High unit price – Low efficiency of raw material usage – Low heat conductivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Machining requires special environment (glass fiber content) – Low heat conductivity
Resistivity at 4.7 K [Ωm]	5×10^{-7}	1×10^{-7}	insulator	insulator
Young's modulus @ cryo [GPa]	215	114	18.1 [21](RT value of [21], 11.6 GPa is higher than in Table 2)	22 ([36] for G11)
Integrated thermal expansion from RT to 4.2 K [mm/m]	3	3	3	?

5 Mechanical stability, thermal expansion

Lorentz forces in dipole magnets are trying to make the coil cross-section elliptical: they point outwards in the horizontal midplane, and inwards at the bottom and top. This can lead to cracks in the impregnant epoxy and quenches. Magnet designs where the yoke gives mechanical support to the coils to counteract the Lorentz forces typically display a good quench performance. In contrast to straight magnets, in curved magnets the Lorentz forces also try to make the coil straight. Therefore, for the demonstrator prototype it was decided to use the *support by the yoke* concept. The yoke laminations need an external frame to be supported in position along the curvature of the magnet and to be tightened. The laminations transfer the Lorentz forces to the support frame to keep the coil cross-section circular and counteract the straightening forces.

Different thermal contractions of the materials (2 mm/m for iron, 3 mm/m for stainless steel and aluminium-bronze, 4 mm/m for aluminium when integrated from room temperature to 4.2 K) have different effects on the assembly:

- Different contraction in the transverse cross-sectional plane. This can be exploited by a design where the yoke is made of two halves, which are closing onto the coil horizontally to provide a perfect contact or some pre-stress, counteracting the Lorentz forces.
- Different longitudinal contraction between the support frame, the yoke, and the coil. This can lead to large frictional forces between the coil and the yoke, for example
- Different bending radii of the coil and the support frame at cold. With a room-temperature bending radius of $\rho=1650$ mm an aluminium frame would end up at $\rho=1643.4$ mm, whereas an aluminium-bronze coil would have $\rho=1645$ mm at cold.

6 Winding, impregnation and insulation

6.1 Choice of conductor

Low-loss strands left over from the DISCORAP project [13], produced by Bruker, were chosen for this project as a natural cost-saving option. The parameters of the strand are summarized in Table 1. In order to reduce the inductance of the magnet, the strands are arranged into a 6+1 twisted rope, with 6 uninsulated superconducting strands being twisted around a central copper strand. Its role is to assist winding by reducing the stiffness of the rope and to act as an extra stabilizer.

6.1.1 Superconductor wire characterization

The NbTi superconductor wire produced by Bruker EAS (Hanau, Germany) is a customized wire originally designed according to the specifications for the DISCORAP project (INFN – GSI collaboration) [13]. Two billets of wire were produced LF001 and LF002 (divided in 30 and 29 spools, respectively). The wire is now at INFN-Milano-LASA, and has been fully qualified by INFN-Milano-LASA, CERN, and Unige [37]. The main strand specifications by the company are shown in Fig. 12 and Table 4.

As reported in Table 5, the wire has been found of low losses quality, with Nb-Ti filaments of the order of $3.15 \mu\text{m}$. The critical current is relatively low, $J_c = 2297 \text{ A/mm}^2$ @ 5 T and 4.2 K, about 20% lower than the corresponding LHC wire (LHC02 or outer layer strand) [14], which is in line with expectation for fine filament low losses wires (see Table 6 and Fig. 13). The RRR is pretty good, as expected, above 130.

- Strand Typ LF = F58464
- SnAg5 coated strand $\varnothing \approx 0.821$ mm
- Cu / CuMn0.5 : NbTi ≈ 1.36
- Twist length ≈ 6.6 mm

Figure 12: NbTi superconductor wire: company specifications.

Table 4: Critical current, n value and RRR from Bruker.

Parameter	LF001 - 1 beginning of coating beginning of billet 1	LF001 - 30 end of coating end of billet 1	LF002 - 1 beginning of coating beginning of billet 2	LF002 - 29 end of coating end of billet 2
Mikrometer \varnothing average [mm]	0,822	0,823	0,820	0,820
Cu / CuMn0.5 : NbTi	1,32	1,36	1,47	1,33
(Ic [A] @ 4 T, 0.1 μ V/cm, 4.22 K)	612	606	600	656
(n @ 4 T, 4.22 K)	35	32	36	38
Ic [A] @ 5 T, 0.1 μ V/cm, 4.22 K	501	496	488	534
n @ 5 T, 4.22 K	34	31	33	34
(Ic [A] @ 6 T, 0.1 μ V/cm, 4.22 K)	395	392	383	418
(n @ 6 T, 4.22 K)	31	30	30	31
(Ic [A] @ 7 T, 0.1 μ V/cm, 4.22 K)	286	286	277	301
(n @ 7 T, 4.22 K)	28	29	29	28
RRR	135	139	156	147

Table 5: NbTi conductor parameters.

Parameters	Values	unit
Strand type	Round	-
Diameter	0.821	mm
(Cu/NoCu)	1.36	-
Jc (5T @ 4.2 K)	2300	A/mm ²
Ic (5T @ 4.2 K)	516	A
RRR	135	-
Filament diameter	3.15	μ m

Table 6: Critical current measurements and n-value @ 4.22 K.

B	n	Ic10	Ic100	Icrho	Jc
[T]		[A]	[A]	[A]	[A/mm ²]
9	17	78	89	73	345
8	25	181	198	179	804
7	28	293	318	296	1304
6	28	404	438	413	1797
5	35	516	552	529	2297
4	34	629	674	649	2798
3	39	773	820	798	3437
2	40	991	1049	1028	4405

Figure 13: Critical current measurement I_{c10} (and current density J_c) with Electrical field criterion at $10\mu V/m$ @ 4.22 K.

Figure 14: Cross section of the superconducting rope, 6 NbTi strands + 1 central copper strand.

6.1.2 Rope characterization

The cable type is a twisted rope (6+1), i.e. composed of 6 NbTi wires twisted around a copper core wire (Fig. 14). The main reason for using a rope cable is to limit the operating current, offering the double advantage of a lower cost of the power converter and a reduction of the impact of the current leads on the cryogenics [17]. The insulation will be made by a double braid of polyester thread for a whole thickness of about 0.15 mm, and the twist pitch will be of 40 mm. The rope has been characterized by several test campaigns performed by INFN-LASA. Figure 15 reports the table and graph of the critical current measurements of two ropes and their discrepancy with respect to the ideal rope (virgin $\times 6$) being below 0.4%, showing the compatibility of the measurements, and their high repeatability. Figure 16 shows the table and the graph of the critical current measurements performed on the single wires, virgin and decabled. The discrepancy of the decabled wire measurements with respect to the virgin one is compatible with the uncertainty of the measurement system (about 2%), highlighting no degradation introduced by cabling.

$I_{c,10}$ Rope 6+1 [A]				
B [T]	Virgin x 6	1° rope	2° rope	Discrepancy between ropes
9	477	499	498	0.24%
8.4			800	
8.2			998	
8	1088	1136	1132	0.35%
7.8			1271	
7.5		1482	1477	0.34%
7.4			1549	
7	1780	1834		
6.5		2181		

Figure 15: Critical current measurements table and graph of the two ropes measured, and their comparison with respect to the virgin x 6 values.

$I_{c,10}$ [A]					
B [T]	Virgin	Decabled 2		Decabled 1	
9	79.6	80.6	+1.25%	78.3	-1.63%
8	181.3	185.1	+2.13%	182.4	+0.59%
7	296.7	300.0	+1.11%	297.6	+0.29%
6	411.6	414.3	+0.67%	410.0	-0.38%
5	522.0	525.6	+0.70%	525.2	+0.61%
4	642.8	642.6	-0.04%	640.1	-0.43%
3	781.4	781.9	+0.07%	781.9	+0.07%
2	1003.3	993.4	-0.98%	1003.4	+0.01%
1	1441.9	1398.4	-3.02%		
0.5		1754.9			
0		2013.5			

* Discrepancy w.r.t. virgin wire

Figure 16: Critical current measurements table and graph of virgin and two decabled wires, and the discrepancy with respect to virgin wire.

Figure 17: Test winding in the straight aluminium-bronze former.

Figure 18: Polyester braid of the test ropes.

6.2 Winding and impregnation tests

In order to gain experience in winding this particular configuration, 2×8 twisted ropes consisting of 7 dummy Cu strands, insulated by a polyester braid, were wound into the straight aluminium-bronze former (Fig. 17.) described in Section 4.4. The Cu strands were much less rigid than the final NbTi strands. Winding was relatively easy with no pitfalls for this straight former. The polyester braid was stable and did not slip along the ropes. The braid pattern (Fig. 18) proved to be loose and had insufficient coverage. Metallic surfaces were visible through the braid, and all ropes shorted to the formers after a few turns. A better, denser pattern is needed for the final magnet. Another observation is that the sharp outer edges of the grooves can very easily damage the insulation of the ropes during winding. These edges must be rounded during manufacturing.

The test former was given to a company to be retouched (Fig. 19):

- Add fillets to the outer edges of the groove to avoid the damage of the rope insulation during winding.
- Add M6 tapped holes between each turn at the top and the bottom where the wall has the largest thickness. These would allow to install temporary clamps during winding to fix the ropes within the groove.

A second winding test will be carried out with the retouched former as soon as it is available, using the ultimate superconducting ropes (6 NbTi strands around a central Cu strand) which are much stiffer than the dummy Cu

Figure 19: Retouching the straight aluminium-bronze test former.

Figure 20: Wax-impregnated winding being removed from the straight test former.

rope used in the first winding test.

Superconducting coils impregnated with epoxy resins show a training behavior, reaching the nominal current only after several quenches. A recent test on a short Nb_3Sn cable demonstrated [38] that wax can be a better alternative to epoxies, at least in stress-managed coils where an external structure gives mechanical support to the coil turn-by-turn. A test sample impregnated with wax reached the short-sample limit without a single quench. The test coil described above was impregnated with wax using the method developed for the SuShi septum project, avoiding the formation of voids in the wax volume during freeze-out, when wax contracts by about 15%. The molded winding demonstrated a very solid consistency, despite the fact that no overpressure could be applied in the simple setup during freeze-out. A significant force was needed to remove the ropes from the groove. The presence of the polyester braid seems to be an important factor, acting as a retainer of wax to avoid the formation of large voids, in case the refill during freeze-out is failing.

Table 7: Optimized parameters of the winding. For the other parameters required by eqs. (2-5) see Table 1.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Magnet current	I_0	1340	A
Min. rib thickness	$t_{\text{rib,min}}$	0.8	mm
Pitch	φ_0	9.90994	mrad
Coil 1 winding normal curvature		-3.14885	m^{-1}
Coil 1 tilt (groove bottom)	$\alpha_{\text{in}}^{(1)}(\pi)$	-25	deg
Coil 1 tilt (groove top)	$\alpha_{\text{out}}^{(1)}(\pi)$	-35	deg
Coil 2 winding normal curvature		-3.22209	m^{-1}
Coil 2 tilt (groove bottom)	$\alpha_{\text{in}}^{(2)}(\pi)$	-33	deg
Coil 2 tilt (groove top)	$\alpha_{\text{out}}^{(2)}(\pi)$	-40	deg

$\Phi_1^{(1)}$	0.0661898	$\Phi_1^{(2)}$	-0.0775215
$\Phi_2^{(1)}$	-0.00013038	$\Phi_2^{(2)}$	3.15918e-05
$\Phi_3^{(1)}$	4.70658e-06	$\Phi_3^{(2)}$	-1.2673e-05
$\Phi_4^{(1)}$	6.81797e-08	$\Phi_4^{(2)}$	-6.92751e-07
$\Phi_5^{(1)}$	-3.81455e-06	$\Phi_5^{(2)}$	5.44364e-05
$\Phi_6^{(1)}$	-1.31011e-07	$\Phi_6^{(2)}$	1.94963e-06

7 Magnetic design

7.1 Winding parameterization and optimization

Figure 21 illustrates the parameterization and coordinate system used throughout the following analyses. The optimization of the winding geometry has been done by the algorithm described in [39]. In a 2D finite-element model the vertical magnetic field was evaluated on the transverse horizontal axis for axial current distributions of the form $J_\varphi = \cos(n\vartheta) \cdot r/R$ within the cross sectional domain of each coil, where ϑ is the azimuthal angle around the beam, r is the distance from the beam, and R is the inner radius of the thick winding. The factor r/R accounts for the geometric dilution of the wire density due to the radial grooves. The derivatives of the field for each of these current distributions were then evaluated by fitting this data by polynomials, and the weighting coefficients J_n of the $\cos(n\vartheta)$ terms have been determined by linear algebra such that the synthesized currents

$$J_\varphi(\vartheta, r) = \sum_{n=1}^N J_n \cos(n\vartheta) \cdot r/R \quad (1)$$

produce the desired field derivatives (4 T, 0, ...).

Derivation of the winding geometry (3-dimensional center-line at the bottom of the groove) from the J_n coefficients is then made by the following formulae [39]:

$$X = \left[\rho + R^{(i)} \cos(\vartheta) \right] \cos \left[\varphi^{(i)}(\vartheta) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$Y = \left[\rho + R^{(i)} \cos(\vartheta) \right] \sin \left[\varphi^{(i)}(\vartheta) \right] \quad (3)$$

$$Z = R^{(i)} \sin(\vartheta) \quad (4)$$

Figure 21: Illustration of the coordinate systems and variables used to describe the geometry of the curved CCT magnet.

$$\varphi^{(i)}(\vartheta) = C^{(i)} \frac{d_2 R^{(i)}}{n_c} \frac{\varphi_0}{I_0} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{J_n^{(i)}}{n} \sin(n\vartheta) + H \frac{\varphi_0}{2\pi} \vartheta \equiv \sum_{n=1}^N \Phi_n^{(i)} \sin(n\vartheta) + H \frac{\varphi_0}{2\pi} \vartheta \quad (5)$$

where the upper index (i) differentiates the two coils, $R^{(i)}$ is the inner radius of the given coil, $C^{(i)} = \pm 1$ is the tilt of the winding (having opposite signs for the two coils), d_2 is the depth of the grooves (thickness of the winding), $n_c=16$ is the number of conductors in a groove, φ_0 is the angular pitch of the winding, I_0 is the magnet current running in a rope, and H is the handedness of the windings (can be chosen either +1 or -1 for both windings).

For a given magnet current I_0 and minimum rib thickness driven by the choice of the former material, the algorithm described in [39] determines automatically the angular pitch φ_0 , and thereby completely defines the 3D winding paths. As input, the algorithm expects the other geometrical parameters in the above formulae, and the required field derivatives $\partial^n B_y / \partial x^n |_{x=0}$, where x is the horizontal transverse coordinate in the beam coordinate system (lower-case gray letter in Fig. 21). In this analysis a slightly different logic was used: the magnet current and pitch were determined by requiring that the minimum rib thickness is 0.8 mm (the largest value of the considered materials) and the tilt of the inner winding at the bottom of the groove is 25° , giving an average tilt at half of the groove depth of about 30° (see next subsection). The two coils were required to contribute 50-50% to the total field. An alternative option (as outlined at the end of the outlook of [39]) is to allow an asymmetric contribution by the two coils, for example requiring that their maximum excursions are the same.

The values of the optimized coefficients $\Phi_n^{(i)}$ are shown in Table 7. These coefficients show a weak dependence on the exact inner contour of the yoke, therefore the analysis needs to be repeated for the final yoke geometry, or if the ultimately chosen former material allows for a smaller minimum rib thickness.

7.2 Tilt of the winding

When fixing the physical length of the magnet, and the magnet current to a given percentage of the short-sample I_c , the integrated field for CCT magnets has a maximum at a tilt angle (the angle spanned by the

horizontal plane and the approximate plane of a single turn of the given winding) of about 30° [40]. This tilt angle is also a reasonable choice from the point of view of windability, and the general shape of the winding. For a curved CCT, the tilt angle was defined as the angle between the tangential of the winding in the midplane, on the inner side of the magnet (i.e. at $\vartheta = \pi$), and the horizontal midplane.

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha(\vartheta) &= \text{atan2} \left[Z'(\vartheta), \sqrt{X'^2(\vartheta) + Y'^2(\vartheta)} \right] \\ &= \text{atan2} \left[R \cos(\vartheta), \sqrt{R^2 \sin^2(\vartheta) + [\rho + R \cos(\vartheta)]^2 \varphi'^2} \right]\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

At $\vartheta = \pi$ this evaluates to

$$\alpha(\pi) = \text{atan2} \left[R, (\rho - R)\varphi'(\vartheta = \pi) \right]\quad (7)$$

Note that there can be a significant difference between the tilt angle evaluated at the inner surface or outer surface of the winding.

7.3 Curvature of the winding

An important property of a given 3D winding path is whether the wires are pulling into, or out of the grooves when being tensioned. While for a straight CCT, the wires are always pulling inwards, this is not always true for a curved one. If the winding is tilted too much to the horizontal plane, the curvature due to the bending radius will overcome the opposite curvature due to the minor radius of the former, and the wires pop out of the groove when tensioned. This can be checked by evaluating the curvature vector of the winding path (the derivative of the normalized tangential vector of the path versus the arc length parameter) and taking its scalar product with the normal vector of the toroidal surface pointing outward. A negative value means that the path is curving onto the surface, ensuring windability. The smallest possible value is $-1/R$, where R is the inner radius of the winding - this value would be reached with a toroidal winding without a tilt. The curvature is the proportionality factor, relating the tensioning force of the wire to the force pushing a unit length of the wire against the bottom of the groove. For the optimized parameters the curvature requirement was fulfilled, giving -3.15 and -3.22 m^{-1} for the inner and outer coils, respectively, i.e. a pull-in force of about 3 N/cm for a tensioning force of 100 N (see Table 7).

7.4 Yoke laminations

In order to avoid eddy currents in the yoke, and for practical reasons, the yoke is constructed from laminations. Due to the curvature of the magnet, a yoke with a 100% fill factor would require tapered laminations, which would lead to a significant cost increase: besides cutting the contour by laser (rough sections) and wire EDM (precise sections), the laminations should be processed on a 3rd machine, a CNC mill to such a precision that the accumulated deviation in bending angle and position is acceptable over the entire length of the magnet.

The effect of using parallel-face laminations with tapered air gaps has been studied using a reduced 3D COMSOL model of the configuration shown in Fig. 22b, simulating only a symmetry cell between two transverse planes, one at the center of an air gap, and one at the midplane of the lamination (“slice model”). A “magnetic insulation” boundary condition was prescribed at these planes, rendering the magnetic field tangential to these boundaries. For compatibility with these boundary conditions, the prescribed current density distribution within the coil domains was restricted to the axial component (along the curved magnet axis), setting the solenoidal component to zero. The axial current components were determined as described in section 7.1. As a reference, the full 3D magnet was also simulated using the “block coil” model which approximates the coils

Figure 22: Illustration of two configurations with parallel-face laminations, with inner and outer halves of the yoke having (a) different, and (b) the same periodicity. Case (a) has potentially no symmetry, whereas case (b) can be simulated in a reduced 3D FEM model using only one symmetry cell. See text for details.

by contiguous domains containing a continuous current density distribution with both the axial and solenoidal components.

Although the configuration Fig. 22a gives a yoke with a larger fill factor and is a more probable alternative, it has a repetitive symmetry only for special combinations of the parameters, and could therefore not be easily modelled in a simple slice model. Since the analysis presented below only wants to demonstrate that the effect of the air gaps is negligible, this approach is valid, and the conclusions will not be affected by the particular choice of the configuration.

Figure 23 illustrates the vertical field component along the transverse axis x of the beam coordinate system at the center of the magnet (full model) and at the center of a lamination and an air gap (slice model), for a linear iron (left column) and a nonlinear iron (right column). The lamination thickness was chosen to be 5 mm, with a 0.1 mm gap between neighbouring laminations at the inside edge of the yoke (i.e. at $R = \rho - R_{2,yoke}$). The bottom plots zoom into the plateau.

For a linear iron (left column) the solid black line 1 (full 3D block coil model) and dash-dotted green line 2 (slice model with 100% yoke fill factor) are practically identical within the aperture, illustrating the compatibility of the slice and full 3D models. The red solid line 3 (slice model, lamination center) and blue dashed line 4 (slice model, air gap center) are identical within the aperture, indicating the absence of axial field modulation due to the periodic, inhomogeneous yoke structure with the actual parameters. Choosing significantly thicker laminations and wider air gaps gradually introduced a clearly visible axial modulation, proving that the absence of this modulation is not an artefact (failure) of the model itself, but the result of the actual values of the parameters. The aperture field has a negligibly lower value than for the bulk yoke, and a very small quadrupole component - much less than the effects of the nonlinear iron, as shown later. The slightly lower value of the aperture field can be explained by the reduced average permeability of the yoke due to the air gaps.

The aperture field slightly overshoots the prescribed 4 T, the reason for which is not understood. The solid black line of Figure 24 shows the vertical field along the magnet axis for a linear yoke material.

The right column of Fig. 23 demonstrates that for nonlinear iron the aperture field is reduced, and nonlinear field components appear in both the 3D block coil model and the slice model. The reduction of the aperture field (with respect to the 4 Tesla value for the linear iron) is much more significant for the slice model with parallel-face laminations (red solid line 8, blue dashed line 9), than for the full 3D model with a bulk yoke (solid black line 6). However, this drop is partially due to an artefact of the model. While in the full 3D model the magnetic flux in the yoke can expand longitudinally towards the ends (into the fringe field region) and

Figure 23: Vertical field along the transverse beam coordinate system axis x at the center of the full 3D model, and at the center of an air gap or lamination of the slice model. Left column: linear yoke material; right column: using a nonlinear B-H curved for the yoke material.

thereby reduce the flux density and saturation effects in the yoke at the center (where the transverse plot is created), the symmetry constraints of the slice model prescribe longitudinal invariance, and constrain all flux lines to remain within the symmetry cell. This leads to a larger magnitude of the field in the yoke (red line 8 in Fig. 23c), and stronger saturation effects. This artefact is demonstrated by the difference between the black line (6) of the block coil model, and the green dash-dotted line (7) in Fig. 23d, which was obtained from the slice model with a bulk yoke without air gaps. The effect of the air gaps is therefore correctly interpreted as the difference between the green dash-dotted line (7) and the red solid (8) and blue dashed (9) lines, about 0.15 T. The reason is that the reduced amount of iron is driven into saturation earlier in the presence of air gaps; in other terms, in the saturation regime the reduced amount of iron can not absorb the same amount of flux.

7.5 Yoke saturation compensation

If the magnet was to be operated at a single field level, the CCT geometry could have been easily tuned to compensate the field distortions arising from yoke saturation, employing [39]. Nevertheless, field quality must be guaranteed in the whole operative range, so that field quality cannot rely on compensating the yoke at a certain field level. The solution is therefore to modify the shape of the yoke.

Two techniques are proposed for this scope, both based on the same principle. The idea is that, considering the yoke as a field source (with magnetization in place of current), the n-pole component can be reduced by removing the magnetized volumes which are more contributing to it. Ideally speaking, for instance, a

Figure 24: Vertical magnetic field along the magnet axis (arc) assuming linear iron as the yoke material (black solid line) and the nonlinear B-H curve of the typical iron of magnets [ref needed] (red dashed line).

Figure 25: Principles of yoke optimization. Main yoke shaping features(a), and homogeneity of 2D axisymmetric model before (b) and after (c) the 2D optimization process.

sextupole component is corrected removing the portion of the yoke at 60° with respect to the midplane. The most adopted approach is to place holes in the yoke in the region of interest (left, in picture below), but especially giving the small distance between yoke and coil, also “pole shaping” (right, in picture below), is a suitable way to follow. This last technique works having “holes on the edges” between coil and yoke. Fig. 25a illustrates the two features.

7.5.1 Yoke saturation compensation in 2D

A 2D axisymmetric FEM model is set-up in Comsol 6.0. The magnet is therefore simulated like it is a complete toroid. Each layer of CCT is a homogeneous domain where a fixed current density J flows in the out-of-plane direction. For the sake of proficiency, the optimization is performed on a non-ideal yoke shape, in particular to the one from the mechanical option 1.

The optimization is done exploring the parameters space, for holes, notches, and the two together. The field homogeneity in the bending plane of the magnet before the optimization is shown in Fig. 25b. Different lines correspond to different level of current, up to the maximum one. The main component is a sextupole-like inhomogeneity. Considering the holes, the most-effective angle is lower than 60° , around 45° , probably due to the effect of the yoke shape. The larger the hole, the more effective it is, but we limited its diameter to 20 mm. Notches are apparently more effective, even if a depth of 10 mm is ideal to properly reduce the field distortions.

The final solution from the 2D axisymmetric model is a combination of non-symmetric holes and notches. Fig. 25a shows the optimized yoke geometry, which returns the field homogeneity in Fig. 25c. With a mesh of around 25k elements, a single combination requires between 1 and 3 minutes on a desktop workstation (i7, 64 GB of RAM). Given the algorithms in [39], the yoke-shape optimization is a fast but appealing second step for magnet design, necessary when strict field quality is needed over a large range of current values.

7.5.2 Yoke saturation compensation in 3D

The optimized yoke in the previous section has to be validated in 3D simulations before being employed in actual magnets. Different magnet angles (90° , 60° , 45° , 30°) are tested in order to evaluate the degradation of the given optimization. The 90° -case fully retains the optimization quality, the 60° -case homogeneity starts drifting away from the 2D case, the 45° -case shows no improvement with the optimized yoke shape, and 30° -case is actually producing a worse homogeneity with the yoke features as in Fig. 25a.

The obvious reason is that, for such a short magnet, the non-optimized homogeneity is so different from the 2D axisymmetric model that the optimization is actually over-compensating and resulting in a worse quality. Nevertheless, the 2D shape can be taken as a baseline to optimize the 3D model. A reduced (due to the higher computational time) parameter-space exploration is performed. As long as the non-optimized field quality is already better than the 2D model (compare Fig. 26b and Fig. 25b), only holes are considered, mainly for practical reasons: notches require to include a filler between the yoke and the coil, with an additional engineering effort. A symmetric configuration is considered, with holes on both sides. Consistently with the 2D optimization, 20 mm holes are placed below 60° , at 45° .

The optimization procedure resulted in a field homogeneity within the 10 units range on the whole current domain. It is trivial to assess that, given the simplification in the transition between 2D and 3D process, even better field quality can be obtained in 3D. As far as the optimization of the integral field is considered, the 3D coil-homogenized model produces a field quality comparable to the central one, while the full 3D model as shown in Fig. 27 suffers from simplified current-leads and layer-jumps and therefore its homogeneity is not representative of any real magnet. Once the mechanical and connectors design is finalized, the same tools presented in this sections are going to be employed for a full, central-and-integral field quality optimization.

Figure 26: Yoke optimization with 3D model. Yoke shape (a), and homogeneity of 2D axisymmetric model before (b) and after (c) the 3D optimization process.

Figure 27: COMSOL 3D model adopted for yoke optimization (half-yoke shown). Current leads and layer jumps are not depicted because they are not conform to any candidate design.

8 Mechanical design

8.1 Guiding principles

This section summarizes some principles guiding the design.

Vertical rigidity Since the magnet is curved, it can rotate as a rigid body to equally distribute its weight among 3 non-collinear supporting points during handling or installation. Vertical rigidity is therefore less important than for a straight magnet of similar construction.

Coil support by the yoke Lorentz forces acting on the coil are trying to distort its cross-section elliptical (pushing it outwards in the horizontal midplane) and to straighten the curved winding. Since PEEK or pre-preg, having a lower stiffness than metals, is a probable candidate, the yoke should give mechanical support to the coil, and transfer these forces to a rigid frame.

Outer shell An outer shell around the 2nd layer of winding is required to serve as a mechanical interface between the coil and the supporting yoke. The shell should at the same time serve as an envelope for impregnation (wax or epoxy), supporting vacuum, and a few bars of overpressure.

For a detailed description of the 3D FEM simulations see [5]

8.2 Formers

At the time of writing this document, several options are still open to manufacture the formers, see section 4. While the manufacturing steps and the internal structure of the formers may depend on the chosen technology and material, their final shape would be identical. The mechanical design of the magnet is insensitive to the chosen manufacturing method.

8.3 Layer jump

The layer jump concept is illustrated in Fig. 28. It is motivated by the layer jump design developed for the SuShi septum project [41] but in order to save space, the 2×8 ropes bend within the toroidal surface, and out of the surface (transitioning to the outer former) simultaneously. As a consequence, the supporting clamp is consisting of two components to make the assembly simple. Part A is bolted to the former first, clamping down the previous turns of the winding. Part B is bolted as second, maintaining the ropes in the correct pattern and position. The glass fiber tape wrapped around the former - ensuring electrical insulation and alignment between the formers - will be installed enveloping this clamp as well. The shape of the clamp is designed such that the envelope of the inner former and the clamps are convex, so that the glass fiber tape stretches over it tightly, allowing the outer former to be installed easily.

Figure 28: Layer jump concept.

8.4 Yoke and full magnet assembly

During the course of this project two different concepts have been proposed for the mechanical design: one with a yoke containing tapered laminations and a 100% fill factor, and one with parallel-faced laminations interleaved by tapered air gaps. As it was shown in section 7.4, the magnetic design allows for the second choice as well. This model, however, requires individual positioning and support of all laminations. Since there is no earlier experience, and there are no working examples for this concept, and the first concept has reached a much more mature level by the time of writing this report, the first concept is chosen as the baseline design. The second concept is presented nevertheless to document the idea for eventual further R&D projects.

8.4.1 Mechanical Design by CERN and INFN-LASA

This mechanical model has been developed by CERN and INFN-LASA. A detailed explanation of this design can be found in [5]. Here only the main concepts and results of calculations related to this design are reported. Figures 29 and 30 show the assembled view of the mechanical structure surrounding the CCT magnet.

Figure 29: Mechanical structure which surrounds the curved CCT magnet. The demonstrator prototype would have a bending angle of 30° only. (Figure 4.1 of [5])

Figure 30: Internal view of the mechanical structure. (Figure 4.2 of [5])

Figure 31: Main components of the mechanical structure which surrounds the CCT magnet. (Figure 4.3 of [5])

Figure 31 shows the exploded view with the components numbered and listed below:

1. CCT magnet. Some features for azimuthal magnet alignment (initially planned to be plates) are present at the ends of the magnet. These features will be modified since they turned out not to be compatible with the impregnation process.
2. A protection material (0.5 mm thick) made of NEMA (National Electrical Manufacturers Association) G10 that will serve as a mechanical interface between the CCT magnet and the iron yoke, and as an envelope for wax or epoxy impregnation. As a consequence, it must support a vacuum and a few bars of overpressure.

3. At the extremities of the assembly, there are two end plates (made of AISI 316L) which give rigidity to the structure and contain six screws that press on the CCT extremities.
4. Screws that contrast Lorentz forces at the magnet extremities, which tend to make the curved CCT straight.
5. Two small plates, placed at the extremities of the magnet and made of AISI 316L, which must distribute the action of the screws uniformly on the CCT. The small plates are attached to the magnet with glue that can fill possible empty spaces between the magnet and the small plates, thus maximising the distribution of the forces of the screws on the CCT.
6. The iron yoke is divided into two halves that must remain attached to the CCT on the magnet midplane to contain the race track deformation (ovalization of the CCT) given by Lorentz forces (Fig. 32) and stresses of the magnet. The two halves are separated by a gap (not constant, opened at room temperature and closed at cold temperature) whose value was optimized to satisfy two ideal conditions:
 - (a) At the end of the cool down, the gap must be completely closed, while the CCT and iron yoke must have a distance lower than 0.05 mm on the magnet midplane (Fig. 32). This constraint is necessary to maintain a good field quality during the energization of the magnet.
 - (b) When the magnet is energized, the Lorentz forces ovalize the CCT and the iron yoke must contain this effect. For this reason, the magnet and iron yoke must be well in touch on the magnet midplane (Fig. 32) and the gap between the halves of the iron yoke must remain closed. If the gap opens, it means that the iron yoke is not containing the race track deformation of the CCT.

Figure 32: Cross-section of the mechanical structure which surrounds the CCT. In detail B it is possible to see the gap between the two parts of the iron yoke, which is not constant (at the bottom it is smaller than at the top). In detail C it is possible to see the small space between the iron yoke and the CCT due to 1 mm distance between the centres of the iron yoke halves and CCT. This distance is needed to have contact between the CCT and the iron yoke just on the magnet midplane (red circles in the picture). The figure shows additional components with respect to Fig. 31, which are needed for the assembly process (Section 6.3 of [5])

The larger the gap between the iron yoke halves at room temperature, the higher the contact force between the CCT and iron when the magnet is energized, but the risk of not closing the gap between the two parts of the iron yoke at cryogenic temperature is higher. So, the value of the gap between iron halves is a trade-off between the contact of the iron yoke and CCT on magnet midplane and the contact between the iron yoke halves. To find the optimal value of the gap between the iron yoke halves,

different simulations were carried out. Table 8 shows the optimal values of the gap found for different formers materials: the higher the contraction of the material, the higher the gap.

Table 8: Gap between the halves of the iron yoke in case of the different formers' materials. (Table 4.1 of [5])

Former material	Gap top [mm]	Gap bottom [mm]
PEEK GF 30	0.44	0.40
NEMA G11	0.40	0.36
Aluminium 6082-T6	0.54	0.50
Aluminium-bronze 954	0.48	0.44

7. Two clamps are present at the top and bottom of the structure. All the possible materials for the formers contract more than the iron yoke, leading to the detachment between the iron yoke and CCT during cool down. If this happens, the iron yoke cannot contain the deformation of the CCT. So, to avoid this phenomenon, the material of the clamps must have a thermal contraction higher or equal to the one of the CCT formers. The material selected for the clamps is aluminium 6082-T6 due to its high thermal contraction.
8. Four joints with 'c' shape (made of AISI 316L) connect the endplates to the rest of the structure.
9. Screws which fix the 'c' joints to the end plates.

A detailed description of the Finite Element (FEM) simulations carried out to characterize the mechanical behavior of this design can be found in Chapter 4 of [5]. Here just the main results are summarised. All calculations were performed with the initial parameters of the magnet demonstrator requested by HITRIplus (75 mm of bore diameter and 4.5 T of magnetic field), which is a conservative situation since the current parameters (80 mm of bore diameter and 4 T of magnetic field) have a lower magnetic field. This reduces Lorentz forces by about 21%. Thus, decreasing the risk of high stresses and deformations of the CCT magnet and Nb-Ti conductor.

Simulations were carried out in the case of the CCT formers made of four different materials. Tables 9 and 10 summarize the stress results of the formers and the conductor for the four different cases. The following assumptions were made for the stress evaluation:

- The behaviour of the materials was assumed symmetric with respect to traction and compression.
- The stress compared to the limit was the maximum stress in magnitude among Von Mises, maximum principal and minimum principal stresses.
- The minimum required safety factor is 2 since this is a preliminary design. This constraint was well satisfied in all simulations.

The stresses in the formers and conductors are shown in a periodic slice of the magnet in Figures 33 and 34, respectively.

Table 9: Maximum stresses of the formers and safety factors for the different formers' materials. (Table 4.5 of [5])

Formers' Material	Highest Mises Stress [MPa]	Von Stress	Highest Maximum Principal Stress [MPa]	Max-Principal Stress [MPa]	Lowest Minimum Principal Stress [MPa]	Min-Principal Stress [MPa]	Safety Factor [-]
PEEK GF 30	68		40		-65		2.94
NEMA G11	86		41		-82		6.43
Aluminium 6082-T6	97		98		-87		4.59
Alu. Bronze 954	196		90		-172		3.26

Table 10: Maximum stresses of the conductors and safety factors for the different formers' materials. (Table 4.6 of [5])

Formers' Material	Highest Mises Stress [MPa]	Von Stress	Highest Maximum Principal Stress [MPa]	Max-Principal Stress [MPa]	Lowest Minimum Principal Stress [MPa]	Min-Principal Stress [MPa]	Safety Factor [-]
PEEK GF 30	102		123		-52		2.43
NEMA G11	114		140		-41		2.14
Aluminium 6082-T6	75		96		-47		3.13
Alu. Bronze 954	100		70		-84		3

Figure 33: Von Mises stresses of the two formers after cool down and energization of the CCT, expressed in MPa, in case of PEEK GF 30 (a), NEMA G11, aluminium 6082-T6 (c) and aluminium bronze 954 (d). The highest stresses are where there is electromagnetic forces accumulation. (Figure 4.10 of [?])

Figure 34: Maximum principal stresses of the conductors after cool down and energization of the CCT, expressed in MPa, in case of formers made of PEEK GF 30 (a), NEMA G11 (b), aluminium 6082-T6 (c) and aluminium bronze 954 (d). (Figure 4.11 of [5])

Figure 35: Radial (u_ρ) and azimuthal (u_θ) displacements, expressed in mm, of the formers made of PEEK GF 30. (Figure 4.12 of [5])

Several figures of merit were calculated to quantify the change of shape (the deformation) of the magnet due to the Lorentz forces, since this affects the magnetic field quality. The details are in paragraph 4.6 of [5]. All figures of merit remained below the required limit in all simulated cases. This means that the mechanical structure surrounding the CCT succeeded in limiting the deformations of the magnet as desired. Figure 35 illustrates the deformation of the PEEK former due to the Lorentz forces at the centre of a single periodic slice of the CCT.

The assembly procedure [5] uses simple tools: pushing elements and mechanical stoppers, and does not need heavy presses or complex curved elements. This is a big advantage with respect to the traditional Cos-Theta magnet design which requires large presses of about 600-800 tonnes per meter of magnet length. The main steps of the process are as follows:

1. Assembly starts on marble on a horizontal plane where the laminations (Fig. 36) of the single iron yoke halves are placed vertically. In this way, gravity helps to place iron laminations while some stoppers keep the laminations in the correct position (Fig. 37).

Figure 36: Tapered lamination of half of the yoke. (Figure 6.10 of [5])

Figure 37: Single laminations of iron yoke piled up and stoppers, which keep laminations in the correct position. (Figure 6.11 of [5])

2. Some keys are added and spot-welded to the laminations (Fig. 38). This passage is necessary to keep the laminations attached to create a rigid half yoke when the stoppers are removed.

Figure 38: Addition of the keys (Figure 6.12 of [5])

3. After spot welding the keys with the laminations, stoppers are removed and the half of the iron yoke is placed horizontally on the plane. Proper equipment to rotate the structure is required. Some tools (schematized in Fig. 39) will be used to clamp the half of iron yoke to the ground and leave access to the lower part of the structure to insert the clamps and other mechanical stoppers (Fig. 40).

Figure 39: Scheme of the tool that clamps and sustains the iron yoke halves. The tool can slide on the horizontal plane, as indicated by the red arrow in the figure. (Figure 6.13 of [5])

4. Once the iron yoke half is clamped, the CCT is inserted and attached to the iron yoke with temporary support on both extremities of the magnet (Fig. 41 and Fig. 42).

Figure 40: First iron yoke half placed horizontally and clamped to the ground by some tools. (Figure 6.14 of [5])

Figure 41: A curved bar is inserted in the aperture of the CCT to move the magnet inside the iron yoke. (Figure 6.15 of [5])

Figure 42: The curved bar in the aperture of the CCT is removed, and the magnet is kept attached to the iron yoke with two temporary supports (green area). (Figure 6.16 of [5])

- Two mechanical stoppers are fixed to the half of the iron yoke. These stoppers are needed to place the other half of the iron yoke in the correct position (Fig. 43). The mechanical stoppers must have high thermal contraction to not interfere with the rest of the structure during the operational phase.

Figure 43: Addition of new mechanical stoppers to the mechanical structure. (Figure 6.17 of [5])

- Steps from 1 to 3 are repeated for the other half of the iron yoke which is pushed against the mechanical stoppers (Fig. 44 and Fig. 45). After this operation, the temporary supports which keep the CCT attached to the iron yoke are removed.

Figure 44: The two halves of iron yoke before being attached. (Figure 6.18 of [5])

- Then the aluminium clamps are heated and placed to shrink fit with the iron yoke (Fig. 46).
- When aluminium clamps cool down the end plates, 'c' shape joints and screws are added to obtain the final structure (Fig. 47).

Chapter 6 of the reference work [5] also describes the production processes and steps proposed by the CERN's group MME (Mechanical and Materials Engineering).

Figure 45: The tools that sustain the two halves of iron yoke slide horizontally and push one half towards the other until there is contact with the mechanical stoppers. After this procedure, the temporary supports of CCT are removed. (Figure 6.19 of [5])

Figure 46: Addition of the two aluminium clamps. (Figure 6.20 of [5])

Figure 47: Final mechanical structure of CCT magnet. (Figure 6.21 of [5])

8.4.2 Version 2 (alternative design)

This concept has been proposed by Wigner RCP to use parallel-faced laminations, and is illustrated in Figs. 48 and 49. Since each lamination requires individual support, the top (8) and bottom (1) plates have 5 mm deep slots (see Fig. 50), into which the laminations can be slid from the side. Since the tapered air gaps between the neighbouring laminations are rather thin (0-0.6 mm) there is no room to machine a slot for each lamination. Instead, even laminations have a slot in the bottom plate, whereas odd laminations have slots in the top plate. The unsupported horizontal edges of the laminations are sandwiched between the supported edges of their neighbours with a gap between 0-0.6 mm. The extreme vertical edges of neighbouring laminations towards the bending axis are touching each other, providing mutual support, as indicated in Fig. 49.

The assembly frame is manufactured from flat stainless steel sheets for mechanical stability and a thermal contraction matching that of the coil, thereby avoiding different bending radii at cold. The yoke structure is "breathing" longitudinally during thermal cycles, i.e. the laminations translate following the frame and the coil, thereby avoiding longitudinal friction to the coil. Firm contact between the laminations and the coil is ensured by adjustable tapered keys (5). Since stainless steel contracts 3 mm/m down to liquid helium temperatures whereas iron only contracts 2 mm/m, the two halves of the yoke will contract to the coil from both sides by about ± 0.1 mm during cooldown if moving freely, i.e. having a vertical gap between them. Without a room-temperature gap, the structure provides a pre-stress to counteract the Lorentz forces without affecting the coil.

Figure 48: Conceptual magnet assembly with parallel-faced laminations (Concept #2).

The assembly procedure is simple and does not require practically any tooling. It is illustrated in Figs. 51-55:

Figure 49: 2D cross-section of the conceptual model with parallel-faced laminations. The figure has been assembled from several cross-sectional views to grasp the main features at different locations and display them in the same figure.

Figure 50: Slots in the top and bottom plates to support the laminations.

Figure 51: Assembly of the frame and the inner half yoke by sliding each lamination into their supporting slot in the bottom (1) and top frame (8). (Concept #2).

1. The frame is first assembled (Fig. 51) consisting of the bottom frame (1), top frame (8), and the two front plates (11), (12) by the M10 bolts (A). The bolts of the top frame are not tightened, the top frame (8) is lifted by 2-3 mm by the M10 bolts (B). Since the support groove for the laminations is 5 mm deep, the laminations are still maintained in their correct position. The inner half yoke is installed lamination-by-lamination (parts 6 and 7).
2. The coil is placed to the 40 mm wide flat support feature of the inner half yoke (Fig. 52).
3. The outer half yoke is installed lamination-by-lamination (Fig. 53).
4. The yoke keys are installed and held in place by temporary bolts which are not implemented in the illustrative CAD model (Fig. 54).
5. The side walls are installed (Fig. 55). The top frame (8) is lowered by the bolts (B) so that the side walls enter their 1+1 mm deep support grooves in the top and bottom frames (8) and (1). The bolts (A) and (D) are tightened to complete the assembly (Fig. 48). The keys' tightening bolts (C) are adjusted to close the two halves of the yoke, and fixed by spot-welding them to a thin stainless steel rail (not shown).

A quick and simple 2D mechanical simulation taking into account the Lorentz forces on the coils, but ignoring the magnetic forces on the two half yokes, is indicating a displacement of the half yokes by about $\pm 60 \mu\text{m}$ for a frame thickness of 25 mm. More detailed FEM simulations will be needed to verify this concept as a viable alternative.

Figure 52: Installation of the coil to the flat support surface of the inner half yoke (Concept #2).

Figure 53: Assembly of the outer half yoke layer-by-layer (Concept #2).

Figure 54: Installation of the yoke keys to close the two halves. The keys are fixed by temporary bolts which are not implemented in the CAD model yet (Concept #2).

Figure 55: Installation of the walls. The top frame (8) is lifted by the M10 bolts (B) by 2-3 mm so that the walls can be inserted into their support groove in the top and bottom frames. Since the support grooves for the laminations are 5 mm deep, the laminations are still maintained in their correct positions. (Concept #2).

Figure 56: Splices in the "shaking hand" configuration at the front face of the magnet (this illustration has been made with 2×7 ropes in contrast to the 2×8 ropes chosen for this demonstrator).

8.5 Splices

The realization of the splices in the "shaking hands" configuration (see sec. 3) is shown in Fig. 56. The superconducting ropes are exiting the formers axially in order to avoid openings on the side of the coil. A sideways routing of the ropes would lead to a conflict with the yoke, and would be more difficult to seal for the impregnation. The ropes pass through the magnet front plate and enter a splice box, which has individual slots for each splice. Entrance and exit holes of the splice box can be sealed by silicone and the box will be impregnated with wax (with a melting point around $56\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), in order to avoid the movement of the conductors.

9 Conclusions and outlook

While the identification of the manufacturing technology and material of the formers is still an on-going effort, the mechanical structure of the entire magnet is more or less well defined, supported by mechanical simulations. Further efforts will concentrate primarily on finding the best material and manufacturing technology of the formers.

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